

Checklist for data publication – *key information that needs to be provided somewhere*

Title:

Provide a concise and descriptive title for the dataset.

Description:

Your possibility to “pitch” the dataset. Provide a detailed description of the dataset, including its purpose, scope, possible ideas of re-use and any important characteristics.

Explain how the data was collected, processed, and validated.

Creators/Authors:

List the individuals or organization(s) responsible for creating or compiling the dataset.

Provide contact information and affiliation of the responsible authors.

Date of Publication:

Specify the date when the dataset was published or made publicly available.

Versioning:

If applicable, indicate the version number of the dataset; any new versions should be assigned an individual DOI. Describe any changes or updates made as compared to previous versions.

License:

Specify the terms of use for the dataset, including restrictions or permissions.

Choose a suitable open data license (e.g., Creative Commons licenses) to clarify how the data can be used, modified, and distributed.

File Formats:

List the file formats used for the dataset.

If needed, provide information on how to access and open the data files.

Data Structure:

Describe the structure and organization of the dataset, including the names and types of variables or fields.

Provide guidance on how to interpret the data, including any codes or conventions used.

□ Metadata

Include metadata that provides additional information about the dataset, such as units of measurement, variables, test conditions, etc. For in-depth information consult the proposed metadata schemes in the guidelines.

□ Documentation:

Create documentation that explains the context, methodology, and assumptions behind the data.

Include instructions for using the dataset, such as data cleaning procedures or analysis techniques; important: reference your codes!

□ Citation Information:

Provide a suggestion for citation format for referencing the dataset in publications and other works.

Create (and include) persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI), if available, to ensure long-term attribution.

□ Legal/Ethical Considerations:

Describe any ethical considerations or privacy concerns related to the dataset, especially if it contains sensitive or personally identifiable information, comment on informed consent.

Explain how data privacy and confidentiality were maintained during collection and sharing, comment on data's compliance with data protection laws.

□ Acknowledgments:

Acknowledge funding organization and other support-providers for the creation or publication of the dataset.

Recognize contributions from individuals or organizations that assisted with data collection (if not listed as co-authors)

□ Data Preservation:

Bear in mind that data publication does not substitute their archiving/preservation!

Thus, consider long-term preservation and storage of the dataset to ensure its continued availability and usability.